

Water soluble polymer supported silver and platinum nanoparticles for efficient reduction of 4-nitrophenol[†]

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Abstract : Water soluble polymer, poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) [PDADMAC] has been used as the support for the silver and platinum nanoparticles. The supported nanoparticles have been used for the facile reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol using sodium borohydride as the reducing agent. The reduction process is followed by monitoring the change in absorbance of 4-nitrophenolate ion at 400 nm by the UV-Vis spectroscopy. The presence of several isosbestic points indicates a clean transformation of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol. The requirement of the amount of catalyst or reducing agent in the present case is significantly small compared to the previously reported cases, though the rate constant values are comparable to the literature reported values.

Keywords : Water soluble polymer, nanocatalysts, nitrophenol reduction, sodium borohydride, kinetic studies.

Introduction

Synthesis of the stable and size controlled well defined nanoparticles (NPs) has become a subject of immense interest particularly because of their potential use in catalysis¹⁻⁵, optics⁶⁻⁸, magnetics^{9,10} and in biology¹¹⁻¹⁴. The properties of the nanoparticles are different from the bulk material and these properties can be tuned by varying their shape and size¹⁵⁻²³. Synthesis of gold, platinum and silver nanoparticles is particularly important as they are stable, easy to prepare and their properties can be controlled by varying synthetic methodologies²⁴⁻²⁹.

A recent trend in nanoparticle synthesis is to use water soluble polymer support and carry out the synthesis in aqueous medium so that the nanocatalyst can exhibit catalytic activities under environmentally benign conditions³⁰. Gold nanoparticles on various water soluble polymer supports are well studied³¹⁻³³ but silver^{34,35} and platinum³⁶⁻³⁹ nanoparticles supported on water soluble polymer are less explored. Recently, we have reported water soluble polymer poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) [PDADMAC] supported platinum and ruthenium nanocatalysts for the efficient chemoselective hydrogenation and oxidation reactions³⁷⁻⁴⁰. As the above mentioned polymer has emerged as an excellent support for the platinum and

ruthenium nanoparticles, we have therefore synthesized PDADMAC supported Ag⁰-nanocatalyst (**catalyst 1**) and Pt⁰-nanocatalyst (**catalyst 2**) (see Scheme 1) and explored their potential for the effective reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-Nip) to 4-aminophenol (4-Ap) using NaBH₄ as the reducing agent.

As described in the literature that the catalytic performance of the nanoparticles is often measured by the model reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Ap⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. The reduction of 4-Nip in water, without the use of any volatile organic chemical (VOC) is important because of the commercial use of 4-Ap as an intermediate in pharmaceuticals, dye industry, corrosion inhibitors or photo developers^{36,45-47}.

The present article demonstrates the synthesis, spectroscopic, microscopic and powder XRD characterization of **catalysts 1** and **2**. The catalysts have been employed for the effective reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Ap using sodium borohydride as reducing agent, and the reductions have been monitored by the UV-Vis spectroscopy. 4-Nip reacts with NaBH₄ to produce 4-nitrophenolate ion which undergoes reduction in the presence of the catalysts. The rate of the reaction is estimated from the change in absorbance of 4-nitrophenolate at 400 nm with time⁴¹⁻⁴⁴.

The pseudo-first order rate constants of the reactions

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

have been determined and are found to be comparable to the literature reported values⁴⁸. In most of the literature reported cases, the ratio of the substrate to catalyst is very low and the amount of sodium borohydride used is high. From the environmental point of view, apart from avoiding the use of VOC, the reduction in amount of boron and heavy metal containing effluents is highly desirable. In many systems it is also reported that an inert atmosphere is necessary for the effective reduction, and in the presence of air isosbestic points are not obtained as side reactions often compete with the main reduction^{36,41-44}. Therefore, our primary objective is to carry out effective reduction of 4-Nip with minimum amount of catalyst and sodium borohydride. We have also shown that by using **1** and **2** the reduction can be carried out under atmospheric conditions, thereby making the procedure more convenient and practical.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) and sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) were purchased from Merck India Limited. Poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (20% aqueous solution, molecular weight 100000–200000), chloroplatinic acid (H_2PtCl_6), CDCl_3 , D_2O , d_6 -dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) were procured from Aldrich. 4-Nitrophenol, 4-aminophenol and ethanol were obtained from Spectrochem India Limited. Nitrogen gas cylinder was supplied by BOC India Limited. Double distilled water was used for the catalytic studies.

Instrumentation :

A JEOL-JEM-2100F FEG-TEM and JSM 7600F were used for recording the TEM and SEM images of **1** and **2**, respectively. 400 MHz Varian FT-NMR spectrometer and Bruker AV III 400 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer, Perkin-Elmer 950 Lambda spectrophotometer, Magna 550 from Nicolet Instruments were used for recording NMR, UV-Vis and IR spectra, respectively. Silver and platinum contents of fresh and used **1** and **2** were measured by ICP-AES (Arcos from M/s Spectro, Germany). Powder XRD was recorded in Philips powder diffractometer PW3040/60 with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation.

Syntheses of the catalysts :

As described below the syntheses of the catalysts were performed by ion-pairing the PDADMAC with anionic

AgCl_2^- and PtCl_6^{2-} followed by reduction with sodium borohydride (Scheme 1).

Synthesis of Ag^0 -PDADMAC (catalyst **1**) :

A solution of 17 mg (1.006 mmol) AgNO_3 in 2 mL of water was added to 10 mL commercially available 20% aqueous solution of poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC) [molecular weight 100000–200000]. Immediate precipitation of AgCl was taken place. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The above mixture in a round bottom flask was then placed in an oil bath preheated at 333 K and 10 mL 0.01 M NaBH_4 solution was added dropwise with vigorous stirring over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture turned yellow and stirred for 1 h maintaining the temperature at 333 K. The solution was cooled down to room temperature and the volume was reduced to 4 mL under reduced pressure and the brownish-yellow solid mass was precipitated out using ethanol. The filtered solid mass was washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in vacuum to get the catalyst **1**. Silver incorporation : 0.028 mmol/g from ICP-AES analysis.

Synthesis of Pt^0 -PDADMAC (catalyst **2**) :

Catalyst **2** was prepared by following the same procedure as stated for catalyst **1** (Scheme 1). Only 10 mg (0.0244 mmol) of H_2PtCl_6 was used for 10 mL of PDADMAC to get the black solid nanocatalyst **2**. Platinum incorporation : 0.008 mmol/g from ICP-AES analysis.

Catalytic experiments :

Scheme 1. Synthetic routes for the preparation of the catalysts **1** and **2**.

Monitoring the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-*p* is relatively easy and done by the UV-Vis spectroscopy⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. The reactions were carried out in a 3.0 mL UV-Vis cell. To the solution of 4-nitrophenol (1.0×10^{-7} mol in 1 mL water), freshly prepared ice-cold NaBH_4 solution (2.0×10^{-5} mol in 1.75 mL of water) was added. 2.0×10^{-10}

mol of nanocatalyst in 250 μL water ($\text{NaBH}_4/4\text{-Nip}/\text{cat} = 100000/500/1$) was added to the mixture and the change in concentration was monitored by the change in absorbance at 400 nm at 1 min interval.

On addition of NaBH_4 , a strong peak develops at 400 nm for 4-nitrophenolate ion. After addition of catalyst the reduction starts and the peak at 400 nm decreases with time. Decrease in the value of absorbance at 400 nm was measured and from the slope of the plot of $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ [A_t : absorbance at time t and A_0 : absorbance at time zero] against time (t), rate constant (k) values were calculated.

Results and discussion

The first step in the syntheses of **1** and **2** involve ion-pairing of the quaternary ammonium centers (R_4N^+) of PDADMAC with AgCl_2^- and PtCl_6^{2-} . In the presence of excess Cl^- of PDADMAC, AgCl_2^- is formed from aqueous AgNO_3 . Similarly, PtCl_6^{2-} of H_2PtCl_6 undergoes anion exchange with the Cl^- ions of the polymer. Subsequent reduction with sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) produces well dispersed polymer supported metal nanoparticles^{49–51}. It may be noted here that the method of ion-pairing anionic metal precursor with positively charged functionalized solid support to synthesize nanoparticles has been extensively studied by our group and found to be useful for the even distribution as well as stabilization of the nanoparticles^{37–40,52–56}.

Both **1** and **2** have been characterized by spectroscopic, analytical and microscopic techniques. The UV-Vis spectrum of **1** in double deionized water shows a peak at 398 nm and a shoulder at 300 nm (Fig. 1). The peak at 398 nm is attributed to the surface Plasmon absorption band indicating the presence of spherical or roughly spherical Ag nanoparticles, as has also been confirmed by the TEM image⁵⁷. The shoulder peak at 300 nm originates from the polymer support PDADMAC. No peak is observed in UV-Vis region for catalyst **2** as it is black in color (Fig. 1). The IR and ^1H NMR spectra of **1**, **2** (Figs. S1 and S2) are similar to PDADMAC which implies that the polymer backbone remains unaltered after the loading of the metal precursor and consequent reduction. For **1**, the peak for nitrate ion is not observed in IR spectrum and hence the structure of **1** is proposed in Scheme 1.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of PDADMAC, **1** and **2** in double deionized water.

Comparisons of the powder X-ray diffraction patterns (PXRD) of **1** and **2** with that of PDADMAC reveal that the peaks from the polymer remain unaltered (Fig. 2). The five new signals for **1** at 2θ values of 38.2, 44.4, 64.6, 77.6, 81.6 correspond to (111), (200), (220), (311), (222) reflections of *fcc* (face centered cubic) structure of metallic silver (Fig. 2)^{58,59}. In catalyst **2**, a new broad peak at 2θ value of 40.1 suggests the presence of (111) plane of *fcc* structure of platinum (Fig. 2)⁶⁰. These planes clearly indicate the formation of the nanocrystals on polymer support by the complete reduction of the immobilized metal precursors with NaBH_4 . These are in excellent agreement with the Powder Diffraction Files for silver (PDF-No. : 00-001-1164) and platinum (PDF-No. : 00-001-1194). No peaks corresponding to metallic oxides are observed either in **1** or **2**. The size of the particles at (111) plane has been determined using Scherrer's formula. For **1** and **2** the size of the particles has been

Fig. 2. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of PDADMAC, **1** and **2**.

calculated to be 25 nm and 23 nm, respectively. For **1**, the size of the particle (25 nm) is in well agreement with the size determined from TEM studies (20–30 nm). For **2**, due to broadening of the peak, the calculated size of the particle (23 nm) is slightly smaller than that measured from the TEM images (30–50 nm).

The HRTEM images of **1** and **2** show the network like structure (Fig. 3a, b). The distributions of NPs in **1** and **2** reveal different size and shape of the particles. HRTEM images show the lattices (Fig. 3c, d) of the metals. Diffraction patterns of both the catalysts (Fig. 3c, d inset) indicate the crystalline nature of the nanocatalysts.

Fig. 3. HRTEM images of **1** and **2** : (a) and (b) at 50 nm resolution; (c) and (d) at 5 nm resolution and in inset their diffraction patterns.

The reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Ap is a thermodynamically feasible process as is evident from the E^0 values for 4-Nip/4-Ap = -0.76 V and $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3/\text{BH}_4^- = -1.33$ V versus NHE. However, the reaction does not take place in the absence of a catalyst due to a substantial kinetic barrier⁴³. First, sodium borohydride abstracts the OH proton of 4-nitrophenol to form the 4-nitrophenolate ion. During this process the λ_{max} value is red shifted from 317 nm to a strong absorption at 400 nm (Fig. 4).

With the addition of the catalyst the reduction starts and the peak at 400 nm decreases with time and a new peak for 4-Ap gradually appears at 298 nm (Fig. 5). At the completion of the reduction the peak at 400 nm totally disappears and the peak at 298 nm gains maximum intensity (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. The process of reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-Nip) to 4-aminophenol (4-Ap) via 4-nitrophenolate (4-Niplate) and the corresponding UV-Vis spectra.

Fig. 5. Successive UV-Vis spectra of the reaction mixture during the reduction of 4-nitrophenolate by sodium borohydride with (a) **1** and (b) **2** at 298 K.

There are several examples where the reductions are performed in an inert atmosphere of dinitrogen to avoid the aerial oxidation³⁶. The alkaline condition of the reac-

tion medium and the presence of the catalyst generally facilitate the quick oxidation of 4-Ap. The products formed generally by the oxidation of 4-Ap are hydroquinone, benzoquinone or 4-nitrocatechol⁶¹. As mentioned earlier, in this study the entire reduction has been carried out under atmospheric conditions. The appearance of several isosbestic points (270 nm, 317 nm, 465 nm for catalyst **1** and 267 nm, 324 nm, 460 nm for catalyst **2**) proves that there are only two absorbing species in the reaction medium.

The rate of the reduction is calculated from the decrease in the absorbance value at 400 nm assuming the total reduction procedure as a pseudo-first order reaction. From the slope of the plot of $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ against time (t), the value of rate constant (k) is calculated (Fig. 6). The rate constant (k) value for the nitrophenol reduction using **1** or **2** as a catalyst is calculated to be $3.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ or $2.01 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, at 298 K. Though the rate constant values are comparable to those reported for other catalysts, considering the amount of NaBH_4

used, **1** and **2** exhibit much better performance in terms of turn over number (see below) ($\text{TON} = \text{mmol of substrate converted to product by 1 mmol of catalyst}$) and turn over frequency ($\text{TOF} = \text{TON/time}$).

Since most of the earlier reports exhibit low substrate to catalyst ratio and use of large excess of NaBH_4 , one of the main objectives of the work reported here is to minimize the amount of NaBH_4 and the catalyst to substrate ratio⁶²⁻⁶⁶. The highest rate constant $7.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ has been reported by Haruta using gold nanoparticles supported on poly(methyl methacrylate) beads with a substrate to catalyst ratio of 15 only, and the ratio of NaBH_4 to substrate of 1500⁴⁸. Under similar reaction conditions with catalyst **1** and **2**, the kinetics is so fast that, the reduction completes within 30 second. The amount of NaBH_4 is 500–1000 times to that of the substrate in most of the cases reported in literature⁴⁸. To the best of our knowledge only two gold nanocatalysts are reported where the ratio of NaBH_4 to substrate is lower than our present work^{67,68}. Polymer supported gold catalyst is reported by Adler *et al.* with 1 : 1 reducing agent to substrate ratio⁶⁷. Another polymer supported gold catalyst is reported by Dong *et al.* where the NaBH_4 to substrate ratio is 33 but large amount of catalyst has been used⁶⁸. In the present case, optimization of the reaction conditions for reduction has established substrate to catalyst ratio of 500 and sodium borohydride to substrate ratio of only 200.

In many of the earlier reports an induction time for the reduction has been mentioned, and being correlated with the reaction of borohydride and dissolved oxygen at a faster rate than that of 4-Nip and borohydride³⁶. To overcome this problem nitrogen has been purged through the solution in the earlier reports. In the present case, the reduction is carried out under atmospheric conditions and it is observed that initially the reaction is relatively slow for both the catalysts (induction time ≈ 2 min), however when the similar reduction is performed in dinitrogen atmosphere, the same initial time delay is observed again. This can be explained by the time taken for the diffusion of the substrate and hydride ion to the surface of the polymer supported metal particles buried within the polymer chain. The inertness of the catalyst towards deactivation by air is also expected to be slow because of the same reason. Furthermore, the evolved hydrogen in the reaction probably provides a hydrogen blanket that helps in maintaining the oxygen free atmosphere.

Fig. 6. Plot of $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ against time (t) for the reduction of 4-nitrophenolate ion with borohydride in presence of (a) **1** and (b) **2** at 298 K. Initially the reaction is slow and shows the induction time of 2 min.

The catalytic reduction of 4-Nip has been studied at five different temperatures from 298 K to 318 K at 5 K interval maintaining the other conditions of the reaction same. The change in rate constant of the reaction with temperature is linear for both the catalysts (Fig. 7). In all cases the rate of the reaction with **1** is much faster than that with **2**. At 298 K the rate constant value for the reduction using **1** is almost two times than that of **2**.

Fig. 7. Linear variation of the rate constants (k) with temperature (T) for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol with borohydride using **1** and **2**.

From Arrhenius plots the activation energies (ΔE_a) for the reductions are calculated to be 28 kJ mol^{-1} and 52 kJ mol^{-1} for **1** and **2**, respectively (Fig. 8). Usually, for surface catalyzed reactions, the activation energy lies within

Fig. 8. Arrhenius plots : $\ln k$ versus $1/T$ for (a) **1** and (b) **2** from 298 to 343 K with 5 K interval.

the range of $10\text{--}50 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ ⁶⁹. Thus, the measured values clearly indicate that the reduction of 4-Nip with **1** or **2** also occurs via the surface catalytic processes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, water soluble polymer, PDADMAC has been used as a support for silver and platinum nanoparticles. The nanoparticles have been prepared by borohydride reductions of $[\text{AgCl}_2]^-$ and $[\text{PtCl}_6]^{2-}$ ion-paired with the tetraalkyl ammonium groups of the polymer. These two polymer supported catalysts, **1** and **2** are characterized by spectroscopic, microscopic and PXRD studies. The supported nanoparticles are found to be spherical and crystalline, and the size of the polymer supported nanoparticles varies in the range of 20–50 nm. The effectiveness of **1** and **2** has been evaluated in the reduction of 4-Nip to 4-Ap by NaBH_4 . For both the catalysts with relatively small amounts of borohydride, high turnovers can be achieved. The reaction is faster with **1** than with **2**, and pseudo-first order kinetics on the surface of the metal is observed in both the cases.

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Supplementary data

IR and ^1H NMR spectra of water soluble polymer poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride), **1** and **2**.

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